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Wave-powered water pump: artificial upwelling for aquaculture industry

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Abstract

A wave-powered upwelling device can increase the productivity and survivability of several species used throughout the aquaculture industry. This enhancement is due to transporting cold, nutrient-rich ocean water, typically found lower in the water column, to the surface. Macroalgae, like kelp, grown near the water's surface benefit from these altered conditions. By enhancing the growth potential of macroalgae aquaculture, its viability as a feedstock for biofuel is also increased.

UNH's wave-powered water pump uses the relative motion between its float and spar buoy components to drive a single piston pump. Check valves at the pump inlet and outlet direct the flow, while extension hoses increase the vertical reach of pumped water. Instrumentation and a custom-designed, solar-powered data acquisition system were integrated into the device. Both volume flow rate and relative distance measurements from the device were recorded with a synchronized GPS clock. The device was deployed on a mooring adjacent to Appledore Island in Maine and was operational for seven days in March 2023. Environmental monitoring instruments were deployed co-currently to capture wave, weather, above-water video, and underwater acoustic data.

Results from the ocean field deployment indicated the device's performance capabilities in a variety of sea states. The field data was compared to a WEC-Sim numerical model of the device. The numerical model has been used to develop a commercial design of the wave-powered water pump in conjunction with knowledge gained from the field deployment process. The numerical model can be used iteratively for other aquaculture industry projects with minimized cost and effort by simulating devices at each new site location. The efficiency of future devices can also be optimized in the numerical model by modifying device parameters.

This effort provides a valuable design tool and commercial-scale, wave-powered water pump design for use in aquaculture. Next steps include employing the device within a macroalgae aquaculture field to determine its direct effect on growth. Further studies can be completed on the device's potential influence on aquaculture industry and feasibility of a macroalgae biofuel.

Keywords: wave energy; upweller; WEC-Sim; field testing; aquaculture

1. Introduction

The UNH Wave Powered Water Pump (wave pump) enhances macroalgal mariculture by upwelling the colder, nutrient-rich waters from lower in the water column to the surface. The macroalgae can additionally produce more biomass and can continue producing longer through the warmer seasons [1] [2]. Analysis and optimization of the device design and operation was essential to understanding its capabilities. The device's survivability, efficiency, and flow rates in various wave conditions required evaluation. Knowledge of device performance allows for correct sizing to individual mariculture projects. Evaluating the design also created opportunities for design improvement. Field data of device performance was used to validate a WEC-Sim numerical model of the device [3] [4] [5] [6]. A validated numerical model allowed for simulated design changes, which aids in optimization and decision making for development of future models of the device.

Figure 1. Diagram of wave pump device (left), cross-sectional view of wave pump device's piston pump operation (right).

The wave pump is a two-body WEC point absorber device (Figure 1, left). The two main components are a float buoy and a spar buoy. The float buoy is characterized as a 'wave follower' and moves vertically with the waves at the surface. Whereas the spar buoy remains relatively stationary in the water column due to an attached heave plate. Inside the spar was a piston, which was connected to the float buoy. At the lowermost end of the spar was an inlet and outlet pipe system with check valves. As the waves oscillate the float buoy vertically, the motion moves the piston which causes seawater to be pulled and pushed through the pipe system. The inlet was angled downwards to pull in deeper water, and the outlet was attached to a hose that brings the water towards the surface. The wave pump operates by drawing water in on the wave upstroke and pushing the water back out on the downstroke (Figure 1, right). The device was approximately 6.7m tall when in its equilibrium position (when there were no waves acting on the device), approximately 4.9m of which were submerged when deployed. The float buoy was 1.5m in diameter. The heave plate at the bottom of the spar buoy helps inhibit vertical motion of the spar buoy due to wave action. The spar buoy was constructed from a Schedule 40, size 8 PVC pipe. The wave pump device's total weight was estimated at 308 kilograms.

The piston cylinder was a size 4 PVC pipe that was installed inside the main spar float PVC pipe. The piston was an aluminum 6061 cylinder which was machined to contain three O-ring grooves. The piston was attached to a piston rod, made of 316SS. The rod is comprised of three, 1.2m long sections, which were joined together with small threaded rods. The maximum stroke length for the device was 1.2m and was constrained by stopper plates and compression springs. In preparation for an ocean field deployment, hardware modifications made to the existing device increased its durability, corrosion resistance, ability to collect high quality data, and efficiency through hydrostatic adjustment. The team also completed a Biological Assessment and NEPA/environmental permitting review of the field deployment to ensure no adverse effects on local flora and fauna.

During a previous short field test in April 2021, it was demonstrated that the existing wave pump was able to pump water with a single flow rate measurement of approximately 0.45 m^3 per hour [7]. However, prior to the March 2023 field test, the range of pumping flow rates for this device were unknown. An ocean field deployment of the device measuring flow rate, relative motion of float bodies, and wave conditions was conducted to determine device performance. These results were used to validate the WEC-Sim numerical model of the device. The WEC-Sim model and knowledge gained from the deployment were used to improve the design.

2. Methodology

The Isles of Shoals is an archipelago of nine islands off the coasts of Maine and New Hampshire. One of the islands, Appledore, is home to the Shoals Marine Laboratory, which is jointly run by UNH and Cornell University. From the UNH pier in New Castle, NH to the dock on Appledore Island is approximately 11.3km [8]. The mooring field at Appledore Island, ME was selected as the ocean field test site for the wave pump because of the convenience of the moorings installed. The team's familiarity with the location and vessel's ability to travel to the island made it the right choice for the field test. The deployment location was near shore, and the radar tower maintained by SML has an Internet connected camera. This webcam allowed for visual monitoring of the wave pump and Sofar Spotter buoy during deployment.

The water depth at the mooring site was 7.6m deep in MLLW according to the NOAA navigational chart 13283, however SML divers report a depth of 11.3m at MLLW [9] [10]. Given the equilibrium depth of the buoy was approximately 4.9m, there was open water beneath the device of approximately 2.7m to 6.4m. This depth was sufficient for normal device operation given the wave heights at the location. Wave conditions at the Appledore mooring field during March were significant wave heights of approximately 1.2 meters, and up to 3.0 meters with periods of 3 to 5 seconds. These conditions were roughly estimated from the nearby Jeffrey's Ledge NOAA buoy data, which has been shown to be a good estimate of wave conditions at the Appledore site [11] [12].

Instrumentation used in the field deployment included a flow meter, lidar, custom-built data acquisition (DAQ) module, Sofar Spotter buoy, hydrophones, and motion-activated video cameras. The flow meter was from Digen, manufacturer part number: FL-1608. A custom designed and built housing was constructed around the flow meter to protect from water intrusion and transfer the data from sub-surface to the DAQ module. A lidar from Garmin, manufacturer part number: Lidar-Lite v3HP, was used to measure the distance between the spar buoy and float buoy. The custom-built DAQ module was comprised of Arduino Uno, microSD storage boards, GPS clock, power management boards, lithium-ion batteries, and solar panels. The DAQ module stored data with time series accurate to ± 0.012 seconds every twenty minutes. The GPS clock consisted of an Adafruit expansion board compatible with Arduino Uno. To monitor the wave and wind conditions synchronously during the deployment, a Sofar Spotter buoy was moored approximately 90m southeast of the wave pump.

Figure 2. Wave pump device installed on mooring during field deployment (left), Sofar Spotter buoy installed on mooring (right).

On the same mooring as the Sofar Spotter buoy, three to four meters underwater were mounted two Sound Trap ST500 hydrophones set to continuously record at 144kHz. Two motion-activated video cameras from Reolink, Argus 3 Pro, were mounted to the top of the float buoy's gantry. These recorded the immediate surroundings of the wave pump intermittently throughout the deployment.

The wave pump and Sofar spotter buoy were deployed at the mooring field on March 21st, 2023 (Figure 2). The devices were deployed using the R/V Gulf Challenger. The buoy was operational for five days, and then in storm conditions turned on its side for two days. After re-righting the device using a small vessel, the device continued to operate and record data for two days. All equipment and instruments were retrieved and returned to the laboratory in Durham, NH at the conclusion of the field deployment with few exceptions.

3. Results

Outliers were removed from the flow meter data, such that only the 0th to 99th percentile of data remains [13]. This results in an average loss of 0.87% of data, the minimum removal was 0% and the maximum was 1.06% from the 480 twenty-minute files comprising the entire data set when the wave pump was operational (roughly 6.7 days). Outliers were likely caused by electrical anomalies, but their removal does not significantly skew the averaged data, since they comprise on average 0.87% of values. The maximum twenty-minute average flow rate for the deployment was 3.75m³ per hour, the minimum was 0.07m³ per hour, and the average was 1.05m³ per hour.

The flow meter data appeared to consistently respond to the wave forcing throughout the deployment period. The r-value correlating the flow rate to the significant wave height data for the period of March 21st to the 26th was 0.94 ± 0.01 with a p-value of $5.9e-164$. This was a very strong positive correlation, indicating that in larger waves, the flow rate of the device increased. This correlation was determined using the ‘corrcoef’ function in Matlab.

The lidar data recorded the distance between the lidar sensor mounted to the top of the spar, and the lidar’s target which was mounted to the top of the float’s gantry. The distance between these two indicates the relative distance between the float and spar. The lidar data were processed in Matlab with filters to smooth data and remove outliers in twenty-minute increments. Significant stroke heights of the device were then calculated for each twenty-minute file by using peak detection algorithms and averaging the highest third of values. Only the significant stroke heights for which less than 10% of the lidar data was removed by the ‘rmoutlier’ function, and less than 1% was replaced when applying the physical bounds of the possible stroke length were included in the correlation.

The correlation between these two sets of data was a moderate to strong positive correlation between March 21st and 26th. The r-value was 0.79 ± 0.04 and the p-values indicated statistical significance ($2.4e-74$). The strong positive correlation indicated that the wave pump device was both responsive and dynamically efficient in a range of wave conditions. Since the Spotter buoy was measuring wave height, and the lidar was measuring relative distance between two floating bodies, the values were not expected to perfectly correlate or match.

To begin characterizing the performance of the wave pump device in various wave conditions, the average flow rates measured for given significant wave heights and periods were shown in Figure 3 (left). Only wave periods of less than seven seconds were chosen to be represented in this performance map. A clear positive trend was apparent between greater wave heights and increased flow rate, which confirms the correlation between these two data sets.

Overall Device Flow Rate Performance: 3-21-23 to 3-26-23

20 min Avg Flow Meter Data Compared to Spotter Data

Comparing Average Values of WEC-Sim to Ocean Field Deployment Data

WEC-Sim Wave Field Generated Using Sofar Spotter Deployment Data

○ WEC-Sim (6 DOF) * Field Data ○ WEC-Sim (Fixed Constraint)

Figure 3. Performance map of field deployment data (left), WEC-Sim model validation using field data (right).

To validate the WEC-Sim numerical model, the Z-direction elevation data from the Sofar Spotter buoy was used as an input for the wave conditions to the model. Only data from the first five days of field data were considered for the analysis to achieve the most accurate results. The WEC-Sim numerical models were set up to run with each Spotter elevation data in batches of seven and nine on the UNH's Premise High Performance Computing (HPC) cluster. Computations were performed on Premise, a central, shared HPC cluster at UNH supported by the Research Computing Center and PIs who have contributed compute nodes. Given the shared resource of the Premise cluster, a limited number of WEC-Sim simulations were chosen. Twenty-minute field data files which had a range of wave heights and periods were selected to be simulated in WEC-Sim, to provide validation for a range of wave conditions.

Averages of flow rate, stroke height, and stroke period were calculated from each WEC-Sim simulation. Each of these average values from the WEC-Sim model simulations were compared with their synchronous average values from the flow meter and lidar field data. The summary plot which contains these sixteen average comparisons is in Figure 3 (right). For trial number fourteen, the same file was run with both spar constraint conditions: 6 DOF and fixed.

Figure 3 (right) indicates a consistently close relationship between the field data and WEC-Sim simulations for average flow rate, stroke height (or relative position), and stroke period. Amongst the sixteen trials, average percent differences were calculated to indicate the accuracy of the model relative to the field data. The flow rate average percent difference between the WEC-Sim model and the field data was 18.8%. The same average percent difference calculation was performed for the stroke heights, which yielded agreement with an average difference of 22.1%. The average stroke period had an average percent difference amongst the sixteen trials of 15.6%. These low average percentage differences indicate that the WEC-Sim numerical model had a high degree of similarity to the collected field data for the device.

4. Conclusions

What is the relationship between pumping rate and quantity of additional kelp grown? This question relates to the complex nature of an aquaculture operation, which relies upon environmental variability and kelp biological factors. The optimal pumping rate depends upon diffusion methods, sinking rate, and nutrient uptake rate of the kelp. Environmental factors, which vary widely regionally and by kelp farm, additionally add complexity to determining device effectiveness. Some of these factors include water depth, thermocline depth, trophic levels, seasonal variation, and currents. New research in this field is in the process of being published, and the authors have generously shared some of their findings. They have found that for every $1\mu\text{M}$ increase in nitrate, kelp productivity increases by approximately 3.5 dried metric tons per hectare per year in the Gulf of Maine [14]. For a sugar kelp operation in the Gulf of Maine, in water depths of 100 meters, with a one-to-one mixing ratio of deep to surface water, it was estimated that an increase in productivity of approximately 25% can be achieved [14]. Given that every aquaculture operation will differ in terms of species grown, regional location, water depth, and size of the farm, wave pump optimization will look different for every project. Regional location of each operation will lead to seasonal variations in temperature, nutrients, and wave conditions that will vary from project to project. Therefore, optimizing the wave pump for a specific case study is recommended, to examine how all these factors will affect the design.

Wave powered upwelling devices can renewably increase both biomass and growing seasons of aquaculture crops. This boost is attributed to the cold and nutrient dense waters being moved to the surface where macroalgae typically grows. The novel wave-powered water pump device design was successfully proven in a field test with high degree of reliability and durability. Prior to ocean deployment, extensive hardware improvements, instrumentation implementation, and deployment procedures were developed for the device. From the field test results, the device was shown to pump over 3.5m^3 per hour in seas with 0.67m significant heights and periods of five to six seconds. As wave heights increased over the course of the field deployment, flow rates were also shown to increase. The device was also shown to be highly responsive to the wave conditions. A WEC-Sim numerical model of the device was developed and validated using the field data. The WEC-Sim numerical model was shown to have approximately 20% accuracy compared to the field data. This model may be used in the future to increase the scale of future device designs, and reliably predict their performance prior to manufacture and deployment, which saves valuable research resources. Determining optimal flow rates for devices, and number of devices for specific aquaculture operations will aid in determining the benefit of these devices.

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